

Investigating Refactoring Decisions in Data Science vs. non-Data Science Projects

Additional Images and Tables

Figure S_1 reports the participants' expertise levels in other programming languages.

Figure S_1: Participants' expertise levels in other programming languages.

Figure S.2-A presents the combination of knowledge between code smells and refactoring, highlighting with a stripe pattern those participants that were redirected to the example-based questions (one for renaming, and another for moving);

Figure S.2-B shows the responses of that subset (redirected participants) with regards to each term's example.

Figure S.2: Refactoring/Smell knowledge [A]; Striped answers were redirected to the examples reported in [B]. The following example helps to illustrate how to read the chart. In S.2-A, “Good understanding, Frequent use” for the axis “Refactoring Familiarity/Good Understanding, Frequent Use,” the yellow section of the bar represents the number of cases that the participants have good understanding of both smells and refactoring, where they show “good understanding and frequent use” of both smells and refactoring. The green section of the bar represents “Good Understanding, Seldom Use” of “smell” etc.

Figure S_3 shows the familiarity with the IDE's refactoring features (Q9) separated by the years of experience.

Figure S_3: Familiarity with IDE refactoring by years of experience (Q9).

Figure S.4 shows the frequency of manual, IDE-assisted, or combined refactoring, delineated by years of experience (Q12).

Figure S.4: Frequency of refactoring approaches (manual, automatic, combined) by years of experience (Q12).

Figure S.5 shows the different rationales for refactoring and the frequency behind them (Q21)

Figure S.5: Participants' reasons to refactor, separated by refactoring frequency; the percentages indicated exclude the green, intermediate frequency of 'once or twice a month' (Q21).

Table S.1: Challenges classified as top-level codes (themes), finer granularity codes (challenges), and sample responses.

Themes	Granular Challenges	Sample Response (Copied Verbatim)
(General)	Time consuming	A lot of effort, but usually worth it because a class name is so important
Refactoring Issues	Large scale refactoring is challenging	If undertaking a large scale refactoring on a project that has a number of contributors, orchestrating the refactoring and subsequent merge, while also supporting ongoing development and potential hotfixes can be tricky. Git makes life easier than it once was, but it can still be a stressful process
	Identify all instances	Changing the name of all occurrences of this class
	Analyze needs (CS and/or refactoring)	The hard thing is often to decide which part should be really extracted, and how deep with extracting I want to go
	CS identification is difficult	The biggest challenge is knowing how to actually identify a code smell, usually it gets picked up from a code review when a superior reviews my code
Before	Consider the best refactoring solution	Don't have a giant method, neither have a lot of useless method. Try to extract the parts that can be reused in other methods
Refactoring Issues	May require code to be restructured before automated refactoring	Sometimes it requires your code to be in a certain way to be able to apply the automatic refactoring and there is no automatic refactoring to reach that point
	Analyze pros vs. cons	This could also cause bugs and headache if not well thought out, generally a challenge I'd say I face is to action this type of refactoring without considering the risks and it's important to understand the risk and the benefits to every action I take within the codebase
	Scope of refactoring	Adjusting the scope of the method to the new location can sometimes be finicky
	Consider the best code organization	Finding a consisting system to organise methods
After	Apply changes (to related artifacts or same artifact)	Updating all uses of said method and resolving dependencies in new file. Removing dependencies in old file that may not be used anymore.
Refactoring Issues	Traceability	Ensuring that we have accurately tracked uses of that method
	Backward compatibility	If there are problems with compatibility between the old and new libraries
IDE Issues	IDE is complex	Complexity and its slow to start compared to, for example, vim
	IDE is defect prone	Sometimes the renamed item is not found by the IDE in another file and errors arise
	IDE is slow	I do this manually. I think it is faster than select the destination class when you are using the IDE
	IDE lacking features	I got use to doing it manually because the IDE that I used in the past at another company did not have all of the features for refactoring that Visual Studio or even Eclipse had to offer
	IDE makes unnecessary changes	Sometimes the automatic refactoring in an IDE can edit source files that shouldn't be edited. Maybe the variable name that was changed is a local variable and it has also updated the name where it appears in definitions for other classes/functions
	IDE not comprehensive	Sometimes the IDE won't update all uses and I will have to do it manually
	IDE not user friendly	When automatic refactoring goes wrong, the error messages can often be very long and complex - not very human readable. This can put me off using it again

Continue on the next page

Table S_1: Challenges classified as top-level codes, finer granularity codes, and sample responses (cont.)

Top-Level Codes	Finer Granularity Codes	Sample Response (copied verbatim)
	IDE works better with specific OS	At times it just gets in the way of my usual workflow, which is heavily, heavily Linux and terminal-focused for my Python work. On Windows VS sometimes entices me but the calling of WSL is often too strong, unless this is a very Windows-specific program (though for that I tend to go with C# most of the time)
	IDE needs configuration before use	Setting environment path. No nothing led me to avoid using these functionality
	IDE leads to code unfamiliarity	Its More difficult to learn the work when you using automated refactoring
	Lack of tool support	Some IDEs do not have features that can accomplish this
	Different tools have different CS detection rules	Most of the times is choosing the right tool for the job, sometimes we use 2-3 tools and they have different opinions about something. So we had to define our own rules based on our opinions
	Lack of user control when using IDE	I have used built-in IDE tools to do this in the past, but I never really got satisfactory results - there's little control over what file the code goes into, or where the code itself goes within the file. I prefer to create a file manually and copy code over
Knowledge Issues	Lack of IDE knowledge	Final challenge I face is that I found that I am not as good with using Visual studio code as my colleagues. Even with copy and change everywhere I sometimes do it manually because I can't remember how I did it before and if I am pair-programming I feel ashamed to google or ask.
	Lack of knowledge of codebase	Pretty challenging could be making refactors in part of a codebase you're not familiar with
	Lack of knowledge of refactoring	The challenge here is that I'm not sure of an efficient way to implement methods from another code for new pieces of code that are independent, the fastest way here is simply to copy and paste
	Learning curve	The learning curve is the biggest change but after that it is quicker so i will never avoid to use them
	Re-learning how to use IDE	Sometimes remembering how to use the refactoring functions is slower than just doing it manually
	Require refactoring knowledge	Being able to import the functionality of the new module, the right way
	Require codebase knowledge	Need to have a good knowledge of the project structure
	Work with different IDEs	Working with different IDEs
	Require programming knowledge	No knowing that a function I spent time on is built-in in Python base or a commonly used module
	Side Effect	Side effect (deviate from refactoring)
Side effect (affect other functionalities)		Avoiding regression. Sometimes the code has a lot of dependencies. Then the refactor might affect a lot of functionalities
Side effect (broken code)		Code breakages occuring regularly when trying to remove code smells
Side effect (code duplication)		I think the only challenge here is optimization, and duplication of declaration in your code
Side effect (new smells)		Or introducing new code smells when fixing some other
Side effect (program incomprehension)		The readability of the code gets affected

Continue on the next page

Table S_1: Challenges classified as top-level codes, finer granularity codes, and sample responses (cont.)

Top-Level Codes	Finer Granularity Codes	Sample Response (copied verbatim)
	Side effect (more refactoring)	Sometimes it happened to me that when modifying a poorly engineered method, I had to modify other methods in cascade, as the bad practices were reflected in different places in the code. It is definitely a waste of time when I encounter these situations
	Side effect (mess up code format)	Indentation/spacing etc can be annoying to fix as I usually copy+paste for this
	Side effect (update documentation)	Documenting to future developers wherethe refactored code was moved to
	Side effect (increased code complexity)	Another class is added, increasing the overall complexity of the program
	Side effect (code organization)	If there are challenges, it is often because the class hierarchy (far beyond method implementations) is itself arbitrary and confusing, and the 'challenge' here is accepting that as a code smell that should be looked into as part of any simple movement
	Side effect (architectural dependency)	Further imports may be required as well as the potential for circular dependencies if one is sloppy in design
	Side effect (code migration)	Code migration issues can occur if there is lack of planning, or an adequate data migration plan
	May need to sacrifice one dimension for another	I always struggle when I keep growing a class to an unexpected size, and realise that I should refactor it in two or three different classes. However, if I want to be really orthodox, one of them may do very little... it is difficult to keep a balance between functionality and usability
	Developers unaware of potential side effects	Code and behavior can be changed in unexpected ways depending on extraction depth. To better understand the impact of my change, and to better understand how I will have to adapt my testing strategies, I do this manually
	Indication of deeper issue	Ensuring that the "code smell" was not a workaround for around another, more critical issue in the first place, and removing the smell without correctly identifying the deeper problem won't cause the issue to recur more significantly
	Communicate changes with team	Communication with other colleagues to ensure the name change doesn't affect broader functionality. Need to make sure everyone is aware of the change and updates code they are currently working on accordingly
Team/Project	Hard to refactor other's code	However, some code smells written by others are hard for me to understand and thus optimize
Issues	Hard to refactor as a team	It's hard to do refactoring in team. We use git so than we need to resolve merges. Also when comparing git diff you get large amount of changes and it can be hard to keep track what was it before for other team members
	No management support	While I would love to fix them in all the programs I am working on, since they are not technically "errors" the higher-ups usually don't give me the green light since they think it would be a waste of time and would take time away from my actual work
	Different definition of CS for different people	Agreeing on a code smell, one persons smell is another persons ideal solution
	Human aspect (forgetting)	Also when I get back to a project after for example a couple of months, it can be hard to remember how it worked and refactor
Human Aspects	Human aspect (future)	Making sure that the extracted method/variable can be useful afterwards in a different context

Continue on the next page

Table S_1: Challenges classified as top-level codes, finer granularity codes, and sample responses (cont.)

Top-Level Codes	Finer Granularity Codes	Sample Response (copied verbatim)
	Human aspect (trust)	This type of refactoring I always do manually, because I do not trust the IDE enough to do this properly. Since inlined functions are often very short, I just type them myself
	Human aspect (mental)	Challenge I'd say I face with this one is doing something before I have acquired the information it needs, The results? Sleepless nights playing detective on "who's bug is it, anyway" the series, I try to avoid making such mistakes at all costs
	Human aspect (typos, mistakes)	Not extracting everything properly - missing something. Leaving old references in the original class
	Fear of being criticized or criticizing others	Ensuring that when working with others that the developer responsible for the code smell does not feel criticised by the fix for the smell
	Time constraint	In all cases, there is often a deference to the "if it ain't broke don't fix it" attitude, where there is pressure to avoid working on the code smell in favor of something that is more urgently in need of attention as an actual bug affecting real users. I will admit I have my fair share of FIXME comments that end up committed when time is of the essence.
Manual	Manual is error prone	Doing it sometimes by hand, it happens to forget something
	Manual refactoring faster	Sometimes remembering how to use the refactoring functions is slower than just doing it manually
Refactoring	Manual refactoring is hard	Removing code smells manually is difficult
	Manual refactoring more reliable/IDE not reliable	I have performed manual refactoring due to knowing IDE refactoring is going to cause compilation errors in certain situations so I think to myself I may as well do this manually
	Manual effort	Manual editing can cost a lot of time and be inefficient
Codebase Issues	Code dependency	The method or variable might depend on something else, so this has to be taken care of as well
	Coding/naming standard/convention	I guess the biggest challenge is to find an appropriate name that it makes sense and it's readable
	Codebase incomplete	A part of code is missing
	CS cannot be removed (use of certain libraries, legacy code)	And most of the times we have 'code smells' that we can't correct because of some libraries we use that require us to do things in a certain way. Or we have legacy code that can't be touched
	Specific programming language (makes refactoring harder than it should be)	Dynamic languages can make this tricky...you never really know how invokers behave

Table S.2: Results - Refactoring Challenges (Q17)

	[Q17-1] Renaming a class, method, or variable, symbol.	[Q17-2] Extracting a method or a variable from existing code.	[Q17-3] Moving code to another file.	[Q17-4] Inlining a variable or method.	[Q17-5] Changing the signature of an existing function.	[Q17-6] Moving a method up or down the class hierarchy.
Top-3 Challenges	(1.) General Ref. Issues, (2.) Codebase Issues, (3.) After Ref. Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Before Ref. Issues, (3.) Side Effect	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Human Aspect	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Before Ref. Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Codebase Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Before Ref. Issues
Devs. knowledgeable in refactoring, high DS familiarity	(1.) General Ref. Issues, (2.) Codebase Issues, (3.) After Ref. Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Codebase Issues, (3.) IDE issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Codebase Issues, (3.) Side Effect ♣	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Human Aspect, (3.) Codebase Issues ♣	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Codebase Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Codebase Issues (4.) Before Ref. Issues *
Devs. knowledgeable in refactoring, high nonDS familiarity	(1.) Codebase Issues, (2.) General Ref. Issues, (3.) IDE Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Before Ref. Issues, (3.) Codebase Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Before Ref. Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Before Ref. Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Manual Refactoring	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Human Aspect
Devs. unknowledgeable in refactoring, high DS familiarity	(1.) General Ref. Issues, (2.) After Ref. Issues, (3.) Codebase Issues	(1.) Knowledge Issues, (2.) Side Effect •	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Human Aspect	(1.) Knowledge Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Before Ref. Issues ♣
Devs. unknowledgeable in refactoring, high nonDS familiarity	(1.) General Ref. Issues, (2.) After Ref. Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) General Ref. Issues, (3.) Knowledge Issues ♣	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Codebase Issues	(1.) Before Ref. Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect	(1.) Side Effect, (2.) After Ref. Issues, (3.) Before Ref. Issues •
Devs. knowledgeable in refactoring, low DS familiarity	(1.) Codebase Issues, (2.) General Ref. Issues, (3.) IDE issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Before Ref. Issues, (3.) Codebase Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Before Ref. Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Before Ref. Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Manual Refactoring	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Before Ref. Issues
Devs. knowledgeable in refactoring, low nonDS familiarity	(1.) General Ref. Issues, (2.) Codebase Issues, (3.) After Ref. Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Before Ref. Issues, (3.) Codebase Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Human Aspect	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Human Aspect, (3.) Side Effect	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Codebase Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Before Ref. Issues
Devs. unknowledgeable in refactoring, low DS familiarity	(1.) General Ref. Issues, (2.) After Ref. Issues, (3.) Human Aspect	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) General Ref. Issues, (3.) Codebase Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Human Aspect, (4.) Codebase Issues *	(1.) After Ref. Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Side Effect, (3.) Manual Refactoring	(1.) Side Effect, (2.) After Ref. Issues, (3.) Before Ref. Issues
Devs. unknowledgeable in refactoring, low nonDS familiarity	(1.) General Ref. Issues, (2.) After Ref. Issues, (3.) Codebase Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) General Ref. Issues, (3.) Codebase Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Human Aspect, (3.) Side Effect	(1.) After Ref. Issues, (2.) Knowledge Issues, (3.) Codebase Issues	(1.) After Ref. Issues	(1.) Side Effect, (2.) After Ref. Issues, (3.) Before Ref. Issues

• Items 1-2 have an equal number of responses.

♣ Items 2-3 have an equal number of responses.

* Items 3-4 have an equal number of responses.